

CoARA WG TIER – References for Communication and Training on gender bias

Lucio Pisacane (CNR IRPPS), Laura Damiano (UMGC), and Giuliana Rubbia (INGV)

With the contributions of Vanessa De Luca, Claudia Canali, Hana Tenglerova, Sean Sapcariu, Silvia Penati

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Introduction

This document presents references for Communication and training on gender bias suggested by TIER members. It includes information about existing videos and tools to cope with bias in research assessment. A brief description, the link, and an image are provided for each reference.

Analyzed videos

<p>UCLA: 7 videos on implicit bias equity.ucla.edu/know/implicit-bias/</p>	<p>Videos</p> <p>➔ new Implicit Bias Video Series</p> <p>[These videos are intended for public use, but we would like to track how they travel. If you, or your school, organization, company, or club happen to use a video for instructional purposes, please let us know. We're going to keep a public list. And comments are always welcome!]</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Preface: Biases and Heuristics (5:14)2. Lesson 1: Schemas (3:12)3. Lesson 2: Attitudes and Stereotypes (4:13)4. Lesson 3: Real World Consequences (3:45)5. Lesson 4: Explicit v. Implicit Bias (2:49)6. Lesson 5: The IAT (5:14)7. Lesson 6: Countermeasures (5:23)
<p>Interaction and group dynamics in evaluation Committees by NOW www.youtube.com/watch?v=zvRbd40KPyo</p>	<p>The video provided by NOW, the Dutch Research Council, regards Biased Language, Criteria, Structure, Time and Accountability. When the assessment committee convenes, the interaction with the applicants and the group dynamic are very important. Therein may lie challenges leading to a suboptimal assessment. These challenges can play a role during presentations and interviews with applicants, or during the committee meeting in which the assessment of the applications takes place.</p>

The background noise Il rumore di fondo by Italian National Research Council CNR (2023)

The video was produced for sensitizing the evaluation committees on bias in evaluation, including but not limited to gender bias. Checked by Laura and Lucio.

<https://tube.rsi.cnr.it/w/4a1yoWa9QsjHQtrhbrAMb>

Recruitment Bias in Research Institutes by Cerca - Research Centers of Catalonia (2016)

The European gender portal <https://www.genderportal.eu/resources/recruitment-bias-research-institutes> links this video.

The video aims to train male and female evaluators on assessment panels about recruitment bias. This bias - often subconscious - is particularly detrimental to women, leading them to perceive assessment as hostile.

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=g978T58gELo>

Videos to fulfil gender awareness approach by Swiss National Science Foundation SNSF (2024) SPIRIT (snf.ch)

Target: Applicants for research funding. Consider sex and gender in the research topic; Consider gender in the team composition

<https://www.snf.ch/en/nlghrhyzbD90TM9D/funding/programmes/spirit>

Bias in peer review training module by Canadian Institutes of Health Research CIHR, NSERC and SSHRC (2022)

Interactive training module for evaluation committees.
It considers gender and other biases such as age, Institutional affiliation, career stage, anti-Indigenous, and language biases.

cihr-irsc.gc.ca/lms/e/bias/

Balanced, broad, responsible: A practical guide for research evaluators' by FNR- Luxembourg National Research Fund & DORA (2021)

A video for responsible research assessment.
It provides a 'checklist' of six concrete suggestions for research funders seeking to improve responsible assessment of funding applications.

<https://sfdora.org/resource/balanced-broad-responsible-a-practical-guide-for-research-evaluators>

Understanding unconscious bias (2015)

<https://royalsociety.org/topics-policy/publications/2015/unconscious-bias/>

Useful tools and references

	<p>Gvozdanović, J., & Maes, K. (2018). Implicit bias in academia: A challenge to the meritocratic principle and to women's careers – And what to do about it. LERU, N.23.</p> <p>www.leru.org/files/implicit-bias-in-academia-full-paper.pdf</p>
	<p>UCLA Equity, Diversity and Inclusion. (2019). Searching for Excellence. Evidence-Based Strategies for Equitable and Inclusive Faculty Hiring (p. 41). University of California, Los Angeles.</p> <p>https://ucla.app.box.com/v/searching-for-excellence</p>
	<p>NWO – Dutch Research Council: Webpage with practical advice on how to limit <i>implicit bias</i> in recruitment</p> <p>www.nwo.nl/en/assessment-committee-meetings</p>

	<p>NOW Factsheet. The factsheet can be used to help implementing the suggestions given in the video 'interaction and group dynamics in evaluation committees'</p> <p>https://www.nwo.nl/sites/nwo/files/mediafiles/NWO-handout-inclusive-assessment-tools-for-evaluation-committee-meetings.pdf</p>
<p>A METHODOLOGY TO DIAGNOSE BIAS VMware Women's Leadership Innovation Lab Stanford University</p>	<p>Stanford toolbox</p> <p>This tool provides an evidence-based approach to diagnose bias. Diagnosing bias will enable change agents to more effectively design solutions and convince others in the organization that bias does exist in the culture. Diagnosing bias plays essential roles in improving diversity and inclusion program efficacy.</p> <p>https://womensleadership.stanford.edu/resources/tools</p>
<p>Higher Education Quarterly</p> <p>RESEARCH ARTICLE OPEN ACCESS</p> <p>Reconsidering the Assessment Criteria in Academic Recruitment</p> <p>Maria Pietilä¹ Jouko Kekäle² Katri Rintamäki²</p> <p>¹University of Eastern Finland, Joensuu, Finland ²University of Eastern Finland, Kuopio, Finland</p>	<p>M.Pietilä, J.Kekäle, K. Rintamäki (2025). Reconsidering the Assessment Criteria in Academic Recruitment. Higher Education Quarterly, 2025; 79:e70068.</p> <p>https://doi.org/10.1111/hequ.70068</p>

<p>Employment Survey for European Chemists (ESEC3) How Diverse is Europe's Chemical Workforce?</p> <p>Prof. Dr. Reiner Salzer¹ Dr. Nineta Hrastelj² Prof. Dr. Anthony Smith³</p> <p>17 May 2024 https://doi.org/10.1002/chem.202401222</p>	<p>Reiner Salzer, Nineta Hrastelj, and Anthony Smith (2024). Employment Survey for European Chemists (ESEC3). How Diverse is Europe's Chemical Workforce? Chem. Eur. J. 2024, 30, e202401222</p> <p>doi.org/10.1002/chem.202401222</p>
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	<p>https://chemistry-europe.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/chem.202401222</p>
	<p>European University Association EUA online workshop 25 June 2024 Reforming Academic Career Assessment current insights and future directions. Recordings and slides available.</p> <p>https://eua.eu/events/327-reforming-academic-career-assessment-current-insights-and-future-directions.html</p>
<p>Gender Equality in Academia and Research - GEAR tool</p>	<p>GEAR toolkit: Gender Equality in Academia and Research - GEAR tool by European Institute for Gender Equality - EIGE</p> <p>https://eige.europa.eu/gender-mainstreaming/toolkits/gear?language_content_entity=en</p>
	<p>GEECCO. "Deliverable 7.2: Promoting Gender Equality in the Evaluation Process: Guidelines for Jury Members, Reviewers and Research Funding Organizations' Employees", April 2020.</p> <p>https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/documents/downloadPublic?documentIds=080166e5ce76bdf5&appId=PPGMS</p>
	<p>Webinar #2. How can RFOs fight gender bias, SUPERA project (2020)</p> <p>In this webinar, two RFOs who have invested in the understanding of the</p>

	<p>phenomenon and started to take actions will share their experiences: ANR (Agence Nationale de la Recherche) and TA CR (the Technology Agency of the Czech Republic).</p> <p>https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=HJ65dMBAcuU</p>
	<p>Webinar #04: A closer look to unconscious bias and what RFOs can do, SUPERA project (2021).</p> <p>This is the 4th webinar organised by SUPERA and specifically dedicated to gender equality in research funding organisations.</p> <p>https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=G0q-gcWhZZI</p>
	<p>Resources from DORA's Reformscape platform on biases</p> <p>https://sfdora.org/reformscape/source-materials/?_tara_keyword_search=bias</p>
	<p>Toolkit for recognising and rewarding open research (OR4 2021–2027) by UK Reproducibility Network.</p> <p>https://recognition.ukrn-openresearch.ac.uk/</p>

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